

Navigating TechCentral's Innovative Technologies Ecosystem

Report by coursework students of UTS 94663
Navigating Entrepreneurial Ecosystems and
Initiating Change, 2021 cohort

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Foreword

This report is part of a series of student generated series about entrepreneurial ecosystems. Each report is a derivative of their coursework, conducted in collaboration with multiple industry partners and interviews with stakeholders in the ecosystem. The subject, 94663 Navigating Entrepreneurial Ecosystems and Initiating Change, is a core subject in the Diploma in Innovation at TD School and a popular elective across other UTS degree programs. The subject was piloted as part of the launch for the Sydney School of Entrepreneurship in 2017¹ and draws directly on Martin's prior experience in visualising entrepreneurial ecosystems.²

The subject runs for three weeks in July, during which students are tasked with defining and exploring an entrepreneurial ecosystem, understanding its history and visualising its current state. Based on that knowledge, they then develop proposals that will bring the ecosystem forward.

The reports reflect the work that was presented publicly to invited guests and stakeholders in the subject, as well as members of the public who joined the presentations via the publicly available event page.

Methodology

The cohort of 50+ students was divided into random teams, each of which could choose their own ecosystem to focus on, with the only caveat being that it relates to TechCentral. Generally, the ecosystems were geographically in the immediate vicinity of TechCentral³, but varied significantly in terms of their sectoral focus.

Each team was instructed to consider the types of stakeholder based on Stam's seminal (2015) review of ecosystem factors. The general method of this study follows our own method of evaluating ecosystems that has evolved over years of experience, in consultation with an Australian wide network of ecosystem researchers. While our process is not yet well documented, it is entirely consistent with the 2018 guide produced by the German Society for International Collaboration,⁴ promoted by the Aspen Network of Development Entrepreneurs (ANDE). Teams adopt a qualitative approach, involving interviewing a broad range of participants to extract insights on their interpersonal connections and interrelations between factors and to identify specific opportunities for change. Each participant is believed to have a clear view of their immediate ecosystem, from which teams stitch together the more holistic view of how the ecosystem works.

The method can be tailored to specific ecosystems, ranging from rural communities through to internationally acclaimed innovation precincts. The breadth of Stam's framework and this method enables pushing back against the myth that innovation and entrepreneurship is primarily the domain of high-tech startups and VCs. While they do play a very important role, they are not the only organisations that matter to create economic growth (Brown & Mason, 2017; Spigel et al., 2020).

Field research for coursework follows the same principles as field research for academic purposes. As a result, the students' work mirrored the process of ecosystem research conducted by Martin Bliemel, for which he has ethics approval (HREC# ETH18-3020).

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¹ Bliemel, M., Schweitzer, J., Roy, G., Keitel, A., Nicolas, L., Miles, M., ... & Griffith, S. (2019, November). Herding cats to co-create cross-university courses in record time. *UIIN University-Industry Interaction Conference 2019*. University Industry Innovation Network.

² Bliemel, M. (2019). University-based entrepreneurial ecosystems and their visualisations. *University-Industry Innovation Magazine*.

³ <https://www.uts.edu.au/news/innovation/welcome-neighbourhood-tech-central>

⁴ <https://www.goethe.de/resources/files/pdf197/5.-guide-for-mapping-the-entrepreneurial-ecosystem.pdf>

Contents

Foreword	3
Methodology	3
Acknowledgements	3
1 History of innovative technology within Sydney City	5
2 Ecosystem Map Explanation	6
2.1 Education sector	6
2.2 Government sector	6
2.3 Commercial Sector	8
2.4 Tech Central	8
2.5 Accelerators, Incubators and Startups	8
3 Leverage Proposal	9
3.1 Development of Digital Ecosystems	9
3.2 Innovative Technologies Exhibition for Universities and Startups	10
3.3 Why?	10
References	12

1 History of innovative technology within Sydney City

Our chosen entrepreneurial ecosystem has a relatively short history, only recently flourishing in urban and city spaces (NSW Innovation and Productivity Council, 2018). Despite innovation being around for thousands of years, the concept of innovation precincts and hubs within the city, is relatively new. Many world-changing technologies were invented in Australia dating back to Indigenous times including the Boomerang, Woomera and Thermoplastic resins. Fast-forwarding to the invention of the Anthrax Vaccination in 1918, 1926 - The Electronic Pacemaker, 1953 - Mortein, 1961 - Ultrasound, 1992 - Polymer Banknotes, 1993 - Wireless LAN (Backbone for WiFi) and 2003 - Google Maps, these are just a few of the Sydney innovative technologies that have been discovered and invented throughout history (Australian Government, n.d.).

Despite this abundance of inventions, innovation precincts in city spaces weren't as common until the re-urbanisation of Innovation Precincts over the past 25 years. Many companies participated in innovation and technology in suburban and out-of-town locations such as science and technology parks or universities.

However, the re-urbanisation of innovation precincts has brought creativity and innovation right into the more accessible, impactful, and resource-rich areas of Australia, the Sydney CBD (NSW Innovation and Productivity Council, 2018).

Within this flourishing urban life: Startups, Hubs, Accelerators, Incubators and Venture Capitalist Companies really began their journeys in the 1990s to the 2000s with Ignition Labs starting their business in 1994, working with a range of businesses and business sizes (IgnitionLabs, n.d.). Cicada Innovations wasn't far behind, starting in the year 2000 soon becoming Australia's leading incubator for startups and scaleups in engineering and science (Cicada Innovations, n.d.). Other businesses followed, the following included: BlueChilli being founded in 2006, Fishburners in 2011, AirTree in 2014, Sydney Startup Hub in 2017 and UTS Startups in 2018 (Sydney Startup Hub, n.d.) (BlueChilli, n.d.) (Fishburners, n.d.) (Palmer-Derrien, S, 2021).

This innovative technology support in the City of Sydney produced an innovation boom revolutionising the innovative tech market and raising major companies such as Atlassian to become one of Australia's major software companies. In fact, the Australian equity market previously lagged in the global technology trend but over the past 5 years has seen substantial growth and increased investor awareness for ASX-listed Technology Companies. The technology sector still only takes up 3.2% of S&P/ASX 200 including companies such as Afterpay and Nitro Software but has had more ASX initial public offerings than any other sector over the last 5 years (BetaShares, 2020). This shows that there is a significant ecosystem starting to form and this ecosystem is highly significant and important to the future economy. The opening of these hubs, incubators and accelerators are therefore a relevant event and milestone in the evolution of innovative technology in the City of Sydney.

Many major innovation and technology milestones have been reached recently with many still in development and construction. The development of Sydney Technology Park is a business and technology centre in Everleigh housing hi-tech startup companies, venture capitalist companies, banks and legal firms. It was created in 1995 encouraging startup companies to take products of market-driven research through to commercialisation stages. It is highly significant within the innovative-technology ecosystem history, achieving international status within 3 and a half years of operation, partnering with Oxford Science Park, Techneon, Kyoto Research Park and so on (Wikipedia, 2021).

The Sydney Metro is another significant project funded by the NSW Government, revolutionising the train system within Sydney making travel faster than ever before. The Sydney Metro is already in Sydney's North, currently with 13 metro stations and 36km of metro rail. In 2024, when the construction reaches the Sydney CBD and beyond Bankstown, there will be 31 metro stations and 66km of the metro railway for the Sydney people to use (Chris, 2018). This project is still underway and links into the new Tech and Innovation Precinct - Tech Central that is currently under development and will hopefully be completed by 2025.

Tech Central is a major step for the NSW Government towards an innovative tech future, boosting the economy with thousands of new jobs and attracting thousands of students studying STEM to the world-class universities within the city. Tech Central is a hybrid timber tower with solar glass, functioning on 100% renewable energy and stands as the NSW government's answer to Silicon Valley - an innovation and technology precinct on the US west coast (Hendry, 2020) (Weatherley, 2020). It will attract investment and talent from around the world, boosting Australia into tech giant status. Tech Central is part of the

planned “Central Precinct” that will be located in the southern CBD of Sydney, on top of Central Station and stretching down the railway line from Belmore Park to Chippendale and Darlington’s Cleveland Street.

Multiple renovations and projects are to be conducted on these spaces including: Belmore Park, Central Station, Central Square, The Western Gateway, Goulburn Street, Regent Street Sidings, etc (The Urban Developer, 2020). It will be a hub of innovation, startups, scale-ups and tech companies, skyrocketing the economy and Australia’s tech presence in the world.

A recent surge of innovation over the past year is said to be due to COVID-19 and the need for potential solutions to the pandemic both scientific and social. However, this is not surprising due to NSW’s habit of innovative technologies with global impact. “We have a combination of attributes that are hard to beat - solid research strengths (medical technologies, advanced manufacturing, digital technologies and quantum computing to name a few), more start-ups and leading global universities than any other jurisdiction (4 of the 11 are in the top world 200) and a highly-skilled workforce. The industry also invests more in research and development in NSW than any other jurisdiction in Australia, averaging \$6.6 billion in annual expenditure over recent years.” (Upton, G, 2021). This gives an insight into the support that NSW has for its Innovation and Technology sectors, catalysing new and exciting projects with global impact, especially during a pandemic, a time of need. COVID-19 has shone a light on the strong innovative technology capacities of NSW. “Technological innovation is globally significant because it grows the complexity of established but less complex industries and builds new markets in complex industries. And as our economy recovers better and faster than the other places that have shut theirs, there is a once in a generation opportunity to build on that capacity.” (Upton, G, 2021). With COVID-19’s impact globally, NSW’s response to this has given us an opportunity to build on our already strong innovative capacity. Therefore the pandemic is a significant event and milestone in relation to the evolution of innovative technologies within the City of Sydney, changing the ways that people think and approach the development of solutions, shaping the ecosystem to the way that it is today.

2 Ecosystem Map Explanation

2.1 Education sector

Education is an essential sector of innovative technology as it allows for new ideas to flow productively. As it is seen on the ecosystem map UTS, UNSW and USYD are the main universities a part of the city of Sydney. This also links to graduate programs influencing the future of students within the innovation world. UTS startups, Incubate startup program and the Founders Program are an essential sector of this ecosystem Map as they are the foundation of new businesses development, especially for students. Attila Brungs, The Vice-Chancellor of UTS also is a major link to the education sector as he is a passionate advocate for innovation. He believes that universities have the power to prepare and create jobs for the future of students.

The education sector is connected to graduate job programs and the commercial industry as it prepares students and graduates to fill internship and graduate programs, then flowing into the commercial sector of the ecosystem. Education is connected to the NSW Government as they have a particular influence on the policies and rules that universities and schools have to follow.

2.2 Government sector

Government/councils are a major sector of any entrepreneurial ecosystem, setting the policies and rules that that ecosystem must function under. The NSW government and councils are significant in the innovative technology ecosystem as they often fund scientific, innovative and technological projects such as CSIRO, ANSTO, Sydney Startup Hub and Central Precinct. Stakeholders within this sector include the Premier: Gladys Berejiklian, Minister for Jobs, Investment, Tourism and Western Sydney: Stuart Ayres, and Minister for Transport and Roads: Andrew Constance. Other stakeholders include Clover Moore: Lord Mayor of City of Sydney, Geoff Roberts: Chief Commissioner at Greater Sydney Commission, and Monica Barone: Chief Executive Officer, City of Sydney Council.

It is also connected to the NSW Transport as the government approves any projects and work conducted in the transport sector of NSW, especially the City of Sydney. Minister of Transport and Roads: Andrew Constance is a significant stakeholder connected to both the NSW Government and NSW Transport.

The NSW Government is connected to Tech Central due to its significant involvement with the development of the Central Precinct. Tech Central is to be built on top of Central Station and beside the railway from Belmore Park to Cleveland Street, Darlington. The Central Precinct also involves significant renovations to Central Station, upgrading it and the station's surrounding areas.

2.3 Commercial Sector

The Commercial sector is vital to the innovative technology ecosystem as it commercialises and provides financial appeal and aid to smaller stakeholders. Atlassian is currently propelling Australian innovation in the technology sector through their own collaboration and innovation, giving back to the ecosystem through the development of Tech Central within the Central Precinct. Venture Capitalist Companies provide those with sound and potentially successful ideas a financial platform to innovate by putting their plans to action. Startup hubs such as Sydney Startup Hub, UTS Startups, etc are currently connecting and encouraging collaboration between commercialised startups for the development of technology, innovation and the ecosystem.

2.4 Tech Central

There are thousands of entrepreneurial ecosystems in the world. Tech Central is an upcoming innovative, entrepreneurial ecosystem for innovative technology in the central precinct of Sydney CBD. It is said to have a massive impact on the NSW economy, especially Sydney's, bringing international talent and investment opportunities right into the heart of our city.

Atlassian is an Australian software company, supplying products for software developers, project managers, etc around the world. They will house 4000 jobs in Tech Central (NSW govt, 2020) including their Australian head office, being the anchor tenant of the Tech Central Precinct.

David Thodey is the Chair of the Industry Advisory Group for Tech Central therefore he is a significant stakeholder, determining the policies throughout the development of the precinct and guiding the NSW Government to the answer for Silicon Valley. Other significant stakeholders surrounding Tech Central include Co-CEOs: Scott Farquhar and Michael Cannon-Brookes, and Amy Glancey: Chief of Staff, Atlassian. They provide resources, opportunities, policies and partnerships for the ecosystem.

2.5 Accelerators, Incubators and Startups

Accelerators assist a startup in progressing to the next level of its development to be a mature company and incubators to help founders develop their startup while still in the idea stage.

Accelerators and incubators are interconnected as a startup will likely work with both in their progress to become a mature company. Sydney Startup Hub, Blue Chilli, Cicada Innovation, and Fishburners are connected to incubators. Those organizations help founders develop their ideas into startups in collaborative environments surrounded by others that can help, support, and guide them to success. TechSydney, AirTree Ventures, and EnergyLab are connected to accelerators as those organizations help startups step onto the next level of their business development.

3 Leverage Proposal

Innovative technologies are a new era of worldwide competition and economic growth, an ecosystem that is still rapidly growing within the Australian market. The future development of this ecosystem is for a more collaborative and connected EE, working together to build up the foundations and create a flow of the development of ideas to an end product in the Australian market. This involves supporting up and coming startups, entrepreneurs and innovators in physical and digital ecosystems and guiding the NSW Government to put money into the right places, developing a strong, growing ecosystem and economy.

The current ecosystem lacks collaboration and communication, therefore reducing the connections between individuals such as students and large corporations. In 2031, 10 years from now, the innovative technology ecosystem will be interconnected between universities, institutions, large and small corporations, increasing economic growth through collaboration with a consistent flow of university innovation and entrepreneurship graduates into Australian businesses and startups.

The interviews conducted gave us a particular insight into the successes and failures of the innovative technology ecosystem within the City of Sydney, through the eyes of 3 different stakeholders. Each stakeholder described a lack of collaboration between universities, companies and institutions and that we need to focus on the foundations of the ecosystem before trying to add fancy ideas and projects. They also outlined a need for both physical and digital ecosystems to complement each other for more effective and efficient collaboration within and outside of Australia.

Australian businesses will also stay within Australia rather than relocating to the UK or the US to international markets. Upcoming businesses and startups will have the chance to show and offer their innovations and technologies to current Australian businesses to create a cycle of constant support with the first customers of small Australian startups being larger Australian businesses.

3.1 Development of Digital Ecosystems

Based on the interview with Piers Grove, the Co-Founder and Chair of EnergyLab, collaboration and communication are currently lacking in the present ecosystem which leads to poor connections between universities, corporations, and institutions. However, he also stated that distance is no longer an issue to create collaborative environments because of technology.

Based on his answers, the first lever is to develop a virtual ecosystem within the City of Sydney before physical collaborative spaces such as Tech Central can be used effectively. The creation of the virtual ecosystem will lead to a more collaborative environment within the City of Sydney without having to worry about physical boundaries. The virtual ecosystem will encourage digital collaborations between institutions. Universities, corporations, and institutions will be a part of the virtual ecosystem in which these three sectors will be interconnected with each other creating a more cohesive relationship. The virtual ecosystem can also be used to develop a local and untapped talent pool by creating digital internship programs between universities and institutions. Because it is a virtual ecosystem where distance is not an issue, anyone from around the world could be a part of it which will lead to more investments and more exposure for the local ecosystem. Australian companies located outside of Australia can also be a part of the ecosystem since it is virtual, solving the innovators outside of Australia problem. However, local Australian institutions will be prioritized. The virtual ecosystem does not defeat the purpose of a physical ecosystem but it will instead complement and is transferable to the future physical ecosystem such as Tech Central.

The main activators of the lever are the government, corporations, and universities. Creating a massive virtual ecosystem where everything is interconnected will be costly, however with this proposal, the government will take on the brunt of this upfront financial and opportunity cost. This reduces barriers to entry for all commercial stakeholders wanting to get involved and in the long term, will become an affordable and sustainable ecosystem.

Corporations will support the government in developing the virtual ecosystem by giving advice and gradual privatisation by investing in the virtual ecosystem which could lead to a more efficient ecosystem (such as Tel Aviv in Israel and Silicon Valley in the USA). They will also bring innovation to the virtual ecosystem, facilitate the growth of the ecosystem, and generate employment within the ecosystem.

Universities will prepare their students to be a part of the virtual ecosystem. It will work with other activators on how to make the virtual ecosystem to be a supportive environment for students because they are the future generation and innovators within this sector. These three activators complement each other in developing the virtual ecosystem.

3.2 Innovative Technologies Exhibition for Universities and Startups

The second lever is an exhibition conducted between universities and startup hubs, exposing the current projects and technologies to the Australian public including businesses, incubators, accelerators, venture capitalists and larger corporations who could become investors and buyers in the early future. This would begin in the coming years as Tech Central is built and innovation within Australia is expected to increase. From the answers of three interviews, they pointed out some lack of support for the foundations of innovative technology within the City of Sydney including the government putting their money in the wrong direction.

Piers Grove stated that most innovation and entrepreneurship projects and startups are to be driven by small, efficient teams in the future rather than an abundance of innovators all attempting to attack one problem. For this reason, the contingency plan is to target new startups to build their stance in the ecosystem instead of a giant enterprise, guiding the future stakeholders to success in the ecosystem. Moreover, the Australian market is not as attractive as those overseas including the US and UK. Therefore, it is not appealing enough to attract the larger corporations to move their base to Australia due to the cost, lack of market, labour-intensive, time-consuming burden. With government funding put into the right places, this would hopefully cause a shift in the Australian market, making Australia a more attractive place for upcoming and large existing companies to be.

The approach is to attract NSW government funding for upcoming startups and tech projects through an exhibition publicising and exposing the world, Australian companies and businesses to the current innovative technologies that are being developed behind closed doors. The exhibition is targeted at students at Sydney's world-class universities looking to innovate and produce a new, exciting, groundbreaking product or service that can be invested in, bought or sponsored by Australia's leading corporations. Upcoming startups already have to compete with each other on the global market, some successful, others not. With an exhibition to show these ideas, it brings the competition into one space with each startup having an equal chance to publicise their project, product or service and possibly win government funding, be sponsored or invested in by a leading company, accelerator, incubator or venture capitalist, expanding the current 3% of successful startups to a larger percentage.

Based on all of the respondents' opinion, we believe that there is a lack of communication and collaboration between institutions, universities and businesses being quoted "good superficially but dysfunctional effectively". This is due to the substantial differences across institutions and industries including their focus and aims.

Furthermore, all groups lack a common objective: universities focus on study, businesses focus on profit and institutions focus on the greater community good. As a result, there is a low flow of human resources and collaboration between the three groups. These are the reasons that lead to the current problem and future risks. On an OECD comparator scale, Australia is low (10th in the OECD countries by GDP per capita in 2018) compared to the US' 5th (Wikipedia, 2020). With no support foundationally and more money going towards new precincts and places for innovation, there is a danger of creating new under-utilised precincts. The public policy has to aim at developing the ecosystem and attract business to locate in Sydney. Therefore, after Tech Central is built, development of the underlying entrepreneurship and innovation ecosystem as a focus instead of the infrastructure is advantageous to the Australian Economy. The ecosystem also needs to achieve a better, aligned outcome: high standard of living, sustainable jobs and a growing economy.

The activators of this leverage are the NSW Government, Startups, Universities and Institutions, students, incubators and accelerators and Australian businesses. The NSW Government will provide funding to be used within the exhibition of startups and university students' ideas showing and publicising these projects to incubators, accelerators, Australian businesses, venture capitalists and other investors.

3.3 Why?

These levers and activators put forward will create efficient change within the ecosystem providing a stepping stone for Innovative technologies to flourish within the city of Sydney. Through relevant research, via essential stakeholders, the trend of collaboration is seen to be a gap in the market that is very limited

not only in the city of Sydney but as a nation. It is evident the government is an essential activator as they are directly responsible for the funding and foundational work to develop this into a sustainable ecosystem. This stands to develop the Australian economy in the commercial sector substantially by having a global focus on local innovation and simultaneously garnering the attention from some of the most innovative organisations worldwide. Small startups get a new and exciting stage to work upon, harnessing their given potential from working within their smaller, more efficient teams with the opportunity to expand through exposure and acquisition of global funding.

Students will gain a better chance of exposure within the workforce as they have the opportunity to work closely with leading companies within the EE. An important part of the first lever is the potential for inspired and entrepreneurial students to gain extensive amounts of the first-hand experience through the implementation of online internships. Direct collaboration with large local and international organisations helps the future key stakeholders of this industry develop deep-rooted networks, allowing for access to incredible opportunities coming out of university and later on in their careers.

Additionally, these experiences help students figure out what exactly they want to do within the ecosystem and industry, further informing their opinions, ideas and innovations. With the successful implementation of these strategies by universities, it can attract more students to these programs, therefore expanding the reach of the online ecosystem.

Small Australian businesses and large corporations benefit heavily from the proposal and levers put forward as they are exposed to the new, exciting technologies that are being developed by new Australian startups and University students. They are the first to see and experience the innovations, having the chance to invest, purchase, sponsor and support the creations as they make their way into the Australian market. Piers Grove described the idea that current Australian businesses have first access to upcoming projects, support them and invest in their ideas and technologies until the startup becomes a self-sufficient business itself. "In terms of industry, it can be a hugely competitive advantage for existing industries if they're able to be first movers on new technology. So if Australian businesses can be the first customers for some of these businesses, that is a fabulous relationship to have between innovation and existing industry. And if that means that Woolworths winds up with the best checkout technology on the face of the earth, well, that's good for those businesses, particularly if they can invest and participate in those technologies early on." This would create a cycle of small businesses being supported, then becoming the larger businesses that support the new, small businesses. This means that Australian tech is used in Australian businesses and enters the Australian market before international markets, increasing our economic growth.

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